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Preliminary analysis of hydrogen demand for meeting the fuel needs of turbofan engines operating on short-haul flights at a European airport.

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Abstract. The employment of aviation sector for global trade transportation and tourism is in constantly growth. Even if the aircraft engines ensure high thrust force and high produced power, they show negative effects such as noise and pollutant emissions such as CO₂, NO_x, SO_x, and CO. The increase in the aviation industry reliance involves, as consequence, the increase of released pollutant emissions. In order to minimize the impact of this rapid growth, the transitions towards the usage of cleaner fuels is needed. Fuels like hydrogen have the potential to mitigate the greenhouse gas emissions associated with commercial aviation. In this purpose, this paper focuses on the usage of hydrogen as zero-emission fuel in the aviation sector. Firstly, a market study to validate the potential penetration of a short-medium haul hydrogen powered aircrafts operating on Milan Malpensa airport is performed. The analysis consists in identifying the most frequently aircraft models operating in the considered airport and, for them, in recognizing the most common short-medium routes, by estimating the average fuel (kerosene) consumption for each flight and route. With the aim of evaluating the changes in fuel consumption by replacing kerosene with hydrogen in a turbofan engine, the thermodynamic analysis is performed; in particular, the thermodynamic model of a typical turbofan engine running on both kerosene and hydrogen is developed. The turbofan engine selected for this analysis is the CFM-56, a two-shaft high-bypass turbofan engine installed on Boeing 747 and Airbus A320 family commercial aircrafts. The model, that is validated by using data available in the technical literature, allows to estimate: i) the operating conditions of the engine in terms of temperatures, pressures and air cooling flow rates at each component by assuring the constraint on the power balance for both shafts, ii) the hydrogen consumption (at ground speed) and iii) the volume required for storing the needed hydrogen on board the aircraft.

1. Introduction

The aviation sector plays a pivotal role in global transportation, enabling both passenger travel and cargo movement over short, medium, and long distances. It is a key driver of economic

development, international trade, and cultural exchange, providing critical connectivity across the world [1]. In 2018, passenger transport accounted for approximately 81% of global commercial aviation emissions, while air freight contributed the remaining 19% [2]. Aviation contributes about 2-3% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, but its total climate impact is significantly higher due to non-CO₂ effects, such as contrail formation and NO_x emissions, which can potentially double or triple the overall radiative forcing [2,3].

With air traffic expected to continue growing in the coming decades, driven by increasing demand for both passenger and cargo services, aviation emissions could rise substantially unless effective mitigation strategies are adopted [4]. This has spurred intense research into innovative solutions, including the adoption of sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs), hydrogen-based propulsion systems, and improvements in aircraft design and operational efficiency, aimed at achieving net-zero emissions targets by mid-century [5]. The decarbonization of aviation thus represents both a technological challenge and an opportunity for transformative change within the sector.

1.1 Aviation Demand in Europe: Market Segments Overview

The European aviation market is characterized by a diverse range of services catering to both domestic and international passengers. As depicted in Fig.1, intra-European flights represent the largest share of the market, accounting for approximately 68% of total flight movements, reflecting the strong demand for regional connectivity supported by the European Union's single aviation market [6]. Intercontinental flights to and from Europe follow with around 20%, positioning Europe as a critical hub for transcontinental travel [6,7]. Low-cost carriers are responsible for approximately 32% of flights within Europe, demonstrating their significant role in improving accessibility to air travel, particularly for leisure purposes. Domestic flights represent about 6% of the total, playing a key role in connecting remote and less accessible regions. Business aviation, although accounting for a relatively small share, typically 6-7% of movements, remains essential for high-value corporate mobility and specialized services [6,8].

Figure 1. Segment distribution of European aviation

Flights are generally categorized based on distance: short-haul (typically less than 1,500 km), medium-haul (approximately 1,500–4,000 km), and long-haul (over 4,000 km). Short-haul flights account for the majority of operations, representing about 86% of all flights, yet they contribute

a smaller fraction to total aviation emissions due to their lower fuel requirements per trip and shorter distances. In contrast, long-haul flights, while representing only about 4% of total operations, are responsible for approximately 50% of aviation CO₂ emissions due to their extended distances, higher fuel consumption, and the inefficiency of carrying larger fuel loads over long ranges. Medium-haul flights, covering distances between 1,500 and 4,000 km, represent an important segment of commercial aviation, accounting for approximately 10% of total flight operations. Despite their lower share compared to short-haul, medium-haul routes contribute significantly to passenger and cargo connectivity across regional and intercontinental markets, particularly in Europe, Asia, and North America. These flights are often served by both narrow-body aircraft, such as the Airbus A320 and Boeing 737 MAX, and smaller wide-body aircraft, such as the Boeing 787-8, making them a key target for emerging low-carbon technologies and operational optimizations.

Although medium-haul operations represent a smaller portion of total flights, their emissions contribution is non-negligible, estimated to account for approximately 30–35% of global aviation CO₂ emissions, depending on aircraft type, load factors, and flight profile [1,9]. This segment typically operates at higher frequencies on dense regional corridors, increasing cumulative fuel burn. Additionally, because medium-haul flights often operate at cruise altitudes where contrail formation and NO_x emissions have significant climate forcing effects, their overall climate impact extends beyond CO₂ emissions alone [2]. Therefore, medium-haul aviation represents both a challenge and an opportunity for the deployment of sustainable aviation fuels, hybrid-electric technologies, and hydrogen propulsion solutions.

1.2 Hydrogen demand for turbofan engines operating on short-haul flights

Based on these market characteristics, the potential demand for hydrogen in European aviation is primarily expected to emerge in the short- and medium-haul segments, which collectively account for over 70% of the market (domestic and intra-European flights). According to the European Union's Clean Sky 2 and Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking [10] reports, hydrogen propulsion technologies are particularly promising for aircraft operating routes up to 3,000 km, which dominate the European market [10,11]. Studies estimate that hydrogen-powered aircraft could reduce aviation CO₂ emissions by up to 50% by 2050, assuming technological, regulatory, and infrastructure advancements are achieved. Furthermore, the European Union's Hydrogen Strategy identifies aviation as a priority sector for hydrogen adoption beyond 2035, with an estimated hydrogen demand of up to 3.4 million tonnes per year by 2050. This is supported by recent analyses by the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking, which suggest that short- to medium-haul operations, including low-cost carrier routes, represent the most feasible early deployment scenario due to manageable fuel storage requirements and airport refueling infrastructure needs [12]

While long-haul intercontinental flights present higher technical challenges, hybrid hydrogen-based solutions such as hydrogen-derived synthetic fuels (e-fuels) are also under consideration to decarbonize this segment in the longer term. Therefore, the overall hydrogen potential for aviation in Europe must be seen as a combination of direct hydrogen propulsion for regional and medium-haul aircraft and synthetic fuel production for long-haul aviation. Hydrogen has emerged as a promising alternative fuel for aviation, offering the potential to significantly reduce the sector's carbon footprint. Recent studies suggest that the global demand for liquid hydrogen in aviation could reach 17 million tons by 2050, potentially leading to a 9% reduction

in CO₂ emissions from the sector [13]. Hydrogen propulsion systems, particularly fuel cell hybrid electric configurations, are being explored for their applicability in aircraft [14]. However, the widespread adoption of hydrogen in aviation faces several challenges, including the development of necessary infrastructure for production, storage, and distribution at airports [15].

1.3 Aim of the study

This study investigates the feasibility and implications of replacing conventional kerosene with liquid hydrogen in commercial aviation, with a specific focus on short/medium-haul operations. Although the interest in hydrogen as a solution for decarbonizing the aviation sector has grown rapidly, studies available in the scientific literature have largely focused on conceptual designs or isolated thermodynamic analyses of turbofan engines. This reveals a significant gap in assessing hydrogen requirements based on real market data and in performing feasibility studies that evaluate its practical application in real-world scenarios. To fill this gap, this paper is aimed at evaluating the potential usage of hydrogen in a real operating aircraft, by estimating thermodynamic performances and evaluating the feasibility installation on board. As matter of fact, the strength of this study lies in its multi-level approach. Firstly, it bridges a critical gap in current literature by linking hydrogen fuel demand to real-world aircraft activity at a major international airport (Milan Malpensa), identifying actual aircraft models, flight routes, and fuel consumption profiles. Moreover, the developed thermodynamic model allows to define and compare the kerosene and hydrogen-fuelled turbofan engine performances, considering key parameters such as shaft power balance and onboard storage requirements in terms of mass and volume.

The obtained results not only quantify and compare the kerosene and hydrogen consumptions and storages needs but also provide a preliminary estimation of hydrogen demand for short/medium-haul flights, offering actionable insights for future infrastructure planning and fuel logistics at airport hubs.

2. Study Area- The airport of Milano Malpensa

Milan Malpensa Airport (MXP) is Italy's second-busiest airport and the primary international gateway for the Lombardy region. In 2024, MXP handled approximately 28.9 million passengers, marking an 11% increase compared to the previous year. The airport also managed 731,641 tons of cargo, reinforcing its position as Italy's leading freight hub. The airport handles various aircraft types, including narrow-body aircraft like the Airbus A320 and Boeing 737, as well as wide-body aircraft such as the Boeing 777 and Airbus A330. The airport serves both short-haul and long-haul flights, with a network of 200 direct destinations across 81 countries. This extensive connectivity underscores MXP's strategic importance in European and intercontinental air travel[16,17]. By performing a market analysis, the most common routes as well as the most common operating aircraft in MXP have been estimated. Figs. 2a e 2b illustrates the most common short-medium routes and most frequently aircraft models.

Figure 2. Short-medium routes a) and operating frequency of aircraft b) in Milano Malpensa

Looking at Fig. 2 (a), the High-Frequency Routes are those with a high number of scheduled departures, reflecting strong and consistent demand while Low-Frequency Routes include destinations with a smaller number of flights, representing a more dispersed or occasional traffic pattern. Among all the High-Frequency Routes, the most common performed routes Milano Malpensa- Charles de Gaulle with about 7,079 departures (4.2%) over the year. These departures are performed by different aircraft models such as: Airbus A319, A 320, A321, A321neo and Boeing 737-800. In Figure 2(b), the incidence of the aircraft operating in MXP for all the considered routes is illustrated. The Airbus A320 aircraft shows the greatest incidence, accounting for 23.4% of departures over one year. Taking into account these data, the analysis has been performed considering the Airbus A320 operating Milano Malpensa- Charles de Gaulle route. Fig. 3 shows MXP-CDG route and Table 1 summarizes the main details related to this route.

Figure 3. Milano Malpensa- Charles de Gaulle route [18]

Table 1. Milano Malpensa- Charles de Gaulle route Details

Data	Value
Rout Category	Short Houl
Distance [km]	600
Distance [nm]	324
Travel Duration [hours]	3.0
Kerosene specific consumption [kg/km]	3.13
Kerosene total consumption [tons]	1.88

3. Airbus A320: the case study

The Airbus A320 family commercial aircrafts operate for the 23.4% in Milano Malpensa airport. On this aircraft is installed the CFM56 Turbofan Engine that is a two-shaft high-bypass turbofan engine developed jointly by GE Aviation and Safran Aircraft Engines (through the CFM International joint venture [19]).

Its compression section is characterized by:

- i. a large-diameter single-stage fan at the front of the engine accelerates a high mass of air, contributing significantly to the bypass thrust;
- ii. 4 axial stages Low-Pressure Compressor, that further compress the air before entering the high-pressure section;
- iii. 9 axial stages High-Pressure Compressor, which provides a high compression ratio needed for assuring an efficient combustion.

On the other hand, its turbine section includes:

- i) 1 stage High-Pressure Turbine, which extracts energy from the hot gases to drive the HPC;
- ii) ii) 4 stages Low-Pressure Turbine which drive the LPC and the fan through a concentric shaft.

The dual-shaft architecture allows having independent rotation of the high- and low-pressure systems, enhancing performance and efficiency.

With the aim of estimating the behaviour and the performances of the CFM56 turbofan engine, a thermodynamic model has been developed. The model has been ran firstly with kerosene, by calibrating and validating the results with literature data, and the by using hydrogen. For both fuels, the evaluation and then the comparison in terms of storage feasibility on board the considered aircraft is performed.

3.1 CFM56 turbofan engine: model development

The CFM56 turbofan engine has been thermodynamically modelled in Thermoflex Environment. For it, the following assumptions have been done:

mixed with fuel and ignited; ii) The air flowrate (Stream#10) that is mixed with the hot gas (Stream#13) exiting the CC, assuring to have a reasonable operating temperature for the High-Pressure Turbine (HPT) and iii) the air flowrate Stream#11) that is mixed with the gas exiting the HPT (Stream 15) before entering the Low Pressure Turbine (LPT), assuring also in this case to decrease the gas inlet temperature into the LPT.

The High-Pressure Turbine (HPT) extracts energy from the hot gases to drive the high-pressure compressor via a shaft, while the Low-Pressure Turbine (LPT) drives both the low-pressure compressor and the fan. This mechanical coupling enables the continuous compression of incoming air while assuring the engine's thermodynamic cycle.

Downstream the turbines, the combustion gases are expelled through the exhaust nozzle, producing additional thrust and closing the Brayton cycle. The combination of bypass thrust and core thrust defines the turbofan engine's performance.

3.2 Fuel Storage requirements assessment

The hydrogen implementation on board requires a re-design of the storage system in order to take into account the chemical characteristics of this fuel that differs significantly from the kerosene, as it has been highlighted in Table 2.

Table 2. kerosene vs hydrogen characteristics

Parameter	Kerosene	Liquid Hydrogen (LH ₂)
Density (kg/m ³)	804	70.85
Lower Heating Value – LHV (MJ/kg)	43.15	120
Volumetric Energy Density vLHV (MJ/L)	34.7	8.5
Volume required at same energy	1	4
Typical material	Aluminum integrated in wings	Aluminum or composites with cryogenic insulation
Storage temperature	Ambient	-253 °C
Typical tank location in aircraft	Wings	Fuselage
Gravimetric efficiency	~98–99%	~88–90%
Carbon Intensity (kg CO ₂ /MJ)	0.074	0.000

Liquid hydrogen provides a gravimetric energy density nearly three times higher than that of kerosene (120 MJ/kg vs. 43.15 MJ/kg), making it highly attractive for applications where weight reduction is critical, such as in aerospace and aviation.

However, from a volumetric standpoint, kerosene maintains a significant advantage, delivering 34.7 MJ/L compared to just 8.5 MJ/L for LH₂. This discrepancy stems from the very low density of hydrogen, even in its cryogenic liquid form (70.85 kg/m³). Consequently, achieving the same energy content with LH₂ requires considerably larger storage volumes, which introduces substantial challenges related to aircraft design, tank insulation, and spatial integration.

In addition to the volumetric disadvantage, LH₂ tanks tend to be significantly heavier. Due to the need for cryogenic insulation and reinforced structural materials to preserve the fuel at -253 °C, their empty weight is typically estimated at around 5–7% of the stored fuel mass, compared to just 1–2% for conventional kerosene tanks.

Moreover, tank placement differs notably between the two fuels. While kerosene is typically stored in wing-integrated tanks, LH₂ tanks are generally located in the fuselage. This alternative configuration affects the aircraft's center of gravity and weight distribution, potentially impacting aerodynamic stability and necessitating additional structural adaptations.

Considering all these factors, it is evident that the high gravimetric but low volumetric energy density of liquid hydrogen must be carefully evaluated in relation to its operational constraints.

Nonetheless, in terms of carbon intensity, kerosene emits approximately 0.074 kg of CO₂ per megajoule of energy produced, whereas liquid hydrogen is carbon-free at the point of use. This positions LH₂ as a promising alternative fuel for decarbonizing the aviation sector, provided that the associated design and engineering challenges can be effectively addressed.

These characteristics highlight a fundamental trade-off between energy density and environmental performance when evaluating hydrogen as a substitute for conventional jet fuel in aircraft propulsion systems.

4. Results

Results of the analysis are related to the estimation of the thermodynamic performances and the evaluation of the feasibility hydrogen installation on board the aircraft.

4.1 Thermodynamic modeling results

The thermodynamic model has allowed to evaluate the operating conditions of the engine in terms of temperatures, pressures and air-cooling flow rates at each component by assuring the constraint on the power balance for both shafts. The model has been calibrated and validated by using the operating data related to the kerosene operation and by considering the aircraft operation at ground conditions

Table 3 summarizes the results running the engine with kerosene. The obtained results have been validated according to ref [21].

Table 3. Thermodynamic results running with kerosene

	Mass Flow [kg/s]		Pressure [bar]		Temperature [K]	
	model	[21]	model	[21]	model	[21]

Air Inlet	361	361	1.014	1.014	288	288
1	361	361	1.636	1.636	337	337
Fan Exhaust	301.8	301.8	1.636	1.595	337	337
2	59.2	59.2	1.636	1.305	337	314
3	59.2	59.2	3.709	3.709	445.3	445
4	59.2	-	8.912	-	586.8	-
5	1.184	-	8.912	-	586.8	-
6	1.184	1.18	2	1.85	586.8	650
7	58.02	-	8.912	-	586.8	-
8	58.02	56.8	33.37	33.38	878.6	872
9	56.8	56.8	33.37	33.38	878.6	872
Kerosene	1.284	1.284	50	35	298	288
10	0.61	1.18	31.68	33.38	878.6	872
11	0.61		33.37		878.6	
12	0.61	-	8.9	-	879.2	-
13	58.09	58.1	31.68	31.71	1624	1624
14	58.69	58.7	31.68	31.71	1617	1617
15	58.69	58.7	8.9	8.9	1242.9	1244
16	59.3	59.3	8.9	8.72	1239.3	1241
17	59.3	59.3	2	2	870.2	897
Exhaust	60.49	60.5	2	2	865	894

It is worth noting that the modelling results are consistent with those reported in the considered reference. However, the deviations observed for some streams are justified by an optimization of the thermodynamic model, aimed at balancing the power between the two shafts. As matter of fact, the obtained operating conditions assure the power balance for both shafts, as demonstrated in Table 4.

Table 4. Engine Power balance running with kerosene

	FAN	LPC	HPC	HPT	LPT
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Power Demand [MW]	18.1	6.6	27.6		
Power Output [MW]	-	-	-	27.8	26

It is worth noticing that power balance is satisfied for both shafts. As matter of fact, the power output from the HPT (27.8 MW) allows to satisfy the power demand of the HPC (27.6 MW). At the same way, the LPT power output (26 MW) meets the demands of both FAN and LPC (total power demand 24.7 MW).

This model has been modified by considering replacing the kerosene with hydrogen. Results of this new operating condition are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Thermodynamic results running with hydrogen

	Mass Flow [kg/s]	Pressure [bar]	Temperature [K]
Air Inlet	361	1.014	288
1	361	1.636	337
Fan Exhaust	301.8	1.636	337
2	59.2	1.636	337
3	59.2	3.709	445.3
4	59.2	8.912	586.8
5	1.184	8.912	586.8
6	1.184	2	586.8
7	58.02	8.912	586.8
8	58.02	33.75	881.9
9	56.8	33.75	881.9
Hydrogen	0.4813	50	298
10	0.61	32.04	881.9
11	0.61	33.75	881.9
12	0.61	8.9	882.4
13	57.28	32.04	1624
14	57.89	32.04	1617.2
15	57.89	8.98	1240.4

16	58.5	8.98	1237
17	58.5	2	863.3
Exhaust	59.69	2	858.3

It is worth to highlight that running the CFM56 with hydrogen means having a fuel saving compared to the kerosene of about 64 % assuring the same operating conditions and the power balancing of the system. In particular, for the Milano Malpensa route, characterized by a distance to travel of 600 km (see details of the route in Table 1), the kerosene and the hydrogen consumptions amount to 1,878.0 and 669.8 kg, respectively.

The A320 performs this route 29 times for week. It means that, on a yearly basis, about 1,508 voyages are performed. In the hypothesis that all A320s will run with hydrogen on MXP-CDG route, about 1,010 tons of hydrogen are needed.

4.2 Feasibility on hydrogen storage installation

In the Airbus A320 configurations using liquid hydrogen, cryogenic tanks are housed within the fuselage rather than in traditional wing tanks, due to the need for cylindrical shapes and ultra-cold insulation (~ -253 °C). According to refs. [22,23], two or more tanks can be placed behind the cabin's bulkhead in the aft fuselage. Fig. 5 shows the liquid hydrogen tanks placed into the aircraft fuselage.

Figure 5. Liquid hydrogen stored on board A320

As for the volume perspective, based on the internal dimensions of the Airbus A320 fuselage, approximately 3.7 meters in cabin diameter and over 6 meters of potentially usable aft-fuselage space, it is estimated that up to 40 m³ of geometric volume is available for hydrogen storage [24]. According to recent studies on cryogenic tank design [25,26], only 60–70% of the available fuselage volume can be effectively used for storing liquid hydrogen, due to the need for thermal insulation, structural supports, and safety clearances. This results in an effective usable volume of 25–30 m³. For the short-haul route Milan Malpensa - Charles de Gaulle, the needed hydrogen amount to about 670 kg, which corresponds to ~ 9.5 m³. Therefore, the hydrogen needed for the selected route can be fully accommodated within the modified aft-fuselage of the aircraft, without exceeding structural or spatial constraints.

5. Conclusion

This study has been devoted to the evaluation of the potential use of hydrogen in the aviation sector. Firstly, a market study has been carried out for defining the high frequency routes and the most employed aircrafts in Milano Malpensa airport. According to the obtained results, a thermodynamic model of the CFM-56 turbofan engine has been developed, running firstly with kerosene and then with hydrogen. The thermodynamic model has allowed to evaluate, in ground conditions, has allowed the performances and to assure the power balance on both shafts. As matter of fact, the produced power from the HPT (27.8 MW) is able to satisfy the power demand of the HPC (27.6 MW). At the same way, the LPT power (26 MW) allows to supply both the FAN and the LPC (24.7 MW). Besides, the fuels amount on the considered route has been calculated, and the feasibility installation on hydrogen on board the A320 has been evaluated. Results highlighted that the amount of hydrogen needed to perform MPX-CDG route is reduced of about 64% with respect to the kerosene and it fits within the available space in the aircraft fuselage. However, this option results in a reduction of passenger seats. Although this may represent an economic loss for the airlines, the avoided CO₂ emissions, which is translated into avoided costs for the companies (given that under the Emission Trading System the carbon tax is about €80 per ton), could offset these losses. Future works will deeply characterize the thermodynamic model of the system and the will further explore the environmental and economic aspects of hydrogen integration in the aviation sector.

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